

Confronting Finitude: Ubiquity of Death in Albert Camus' *The Stranger* and *The Plague*

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Abstract

Though arbitrary and inevitable, death is a pervasive theme in imaginative literature. Literary writers offer insights into this existential problem that perpetually troubles all humanity. Literary engagement with death is an occasion to reflect on the subject more profoundly in a way not possible in real life circumstances. This paper is a critical reading of Albert Camus' representation of death in his two novels, *The Stranger* (1946) and *The Plague* (1948) to bring out the philosophical reflections on death embodied in the literary texts so as to enable a more insightful understanding of death; an ever baffling phenomenon. This paper, therefore, explores the ubiquity of death in the two novels and the attendant philosophic aloofness towards death. This paper employs Camus' optimistic existentialism prism to delineate death as an existential human problem, which requires critical attention and meditation to enrich our understanding of the inevitable phenomenon in order to confront it.

Keywords: Death, Existentialism, Philosophic aloofness, Finitude, Ubiquity

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1. INTRODUCTION

The continued depiction of death in literature serves to remind us of our own mortality and work as a "continual defence against death" (Seale, 1998, p. 1). Alvarez opines that "perhaps half the literature of the world is about death" (Alvarez, 1990, p. 236). Camus' *The Stranger* and *The Plague* are novels characterized by ubiquity of death, rendered graphically to show its enormity. The novels are manifestations of Camus' thought patterns and philosophical stances on death as an existential phenomenon. Camus' philosophy sprung from the absurdist movement, which focused on life and nothingness. Camus particularly sought to interpret the meaning of life in an otherwise meaningless world. He posits, thusly:

I continue to insist that this world has no meaning. But I know that something in it has a meaning and that is man, because he is the only creature to insist on having one. This world has at least the truth of man, and our task it to provide its justifications against fate itself. And it has no justification but man; hence he must be saved if we want to save the idea we have of life. (Camus, 1960, p. 28)

Sartre, just like Camus, places mankind at the centre of the world; to live and resolve the problems in the universe without relying on any supernatural being. His atheistic existentialism implies that human being's existence precedes our essence, since there is no God to give us essence. Therefore, it is only human beings who are responsible for creation of their essence, which includes creating meaning and purpose for life.

There is great similarity in how Camus and Sartre conceptualize death. Sartre (1956) views death as that which obscures our freedom to exist. In essence, both Camus and Sartre view death as the culmination of the absurd; the finality of mankind. Hakola and Kivisto (2014) argue that awareness of the ultimate finitude prompts us to examine the nature of life so as to lead meaningful lives. Camus' two novels under study broach the theme of death and present characters struggling to decipher the meaning of an otherwise meaningless life and ultimate acceptance of human finitude. Camus seems to indicate that life can only be understood from the point of awareness of man's inevitable end.

Seminal Deaths in The Stranger

Albert Camus' *The Stranger* has three important deaths: the death of Meursault's mother, the murder of an Arab and the eventual death of Meursault. This paper, however, limits itself to the first for the simple reason that Meursault death is.

The death of Meursault's mother is the first to be recorded thus, "YOUR MOTHER PASSED AWAY. FUNERAL TOMORROW. DEEP SYMPATHY." (Camus, 1946, p. 4). The telegram is sympathetic to Meursault who has just lost her mother. Smith (2006) defines sympathy as the effect brought out in human beings, when we imagine that another person's situation(s) is our situation(s). According to Smith, sympathy helps the affected person to reduce grief by sharing it with others. Of concern, however, is the manner in which the sad news is shared to Meursault. The telegraphic message is casual and captures the finality of death and reveals a detached attitude towards death. The hospice management thus exhibits emotional calmness ostensibly because of the awareness that human beings ought to live with and accept the reality of death. This death is Camus' occasion to philosophize on death as a finality, which erases man's achievement. As he puts it in his other novel, *A Happy Death* (1972) published posthumously:

We find our own lives to be meaningless in the face of certain death; we find our actions pointless given that centuries later they would have been forgotten and soon after that the last traces of our very existence will disappear in the voids of space (Camus, 1972, p. 106)

The hospice management announcing the death of Meursault's mother seems to read from the same perspective of Camus and Sartre such that it is pointless to whine about this particular death of a resident of a hospice who had led an alienated life after being neglected by her son. It is also important to note that Camus deliberately uses the word "mother" and not "mom" to refer to Meursault's deceased parent. "Mother" denotes wavering affectionate attachment, between a mother and son, while "mom" is more intimate. The hospice leadership at Marengo is thus aware of this affectionate breakdown between Meursault and his mother, hence their candid splash: "YOUR MOTHER PASSED AWAY." Owing to the fact that Meursault and his mother lived an estranged life, it is no wonder he remains calm and indifferent to his mother's demise, much to the chagrin of the society depicted in the novel. Meursault is thus, the stranger in the novel who even at the most devastating circumstances, such as that of his mother's death, remains unmoved.

The second death in the novel is that of the unnamed Arab, who is murdered by Meursault in cold blood. This death heightens the place of racism unto death in Camusian fictional society presented in the novel. Azar (2010) argues that the existential themes in *The Stranger* overshadow the otherization nature of the French rule in colonial Algeria. However, Camus' text seems to cast Arabs in a bad light. Ladjal and

Bensaid (2010) argue that largely, the French supremacists in Algeria depicted European collective conscience. This conscience, Ladjal and Bensaid hold that it engendered negative generalizations towards Algerians and Muslims. It is no wonder that Camus' Arab characters in the text are unnamed and listless, which smacks racism in the novel. Karagic (2013) posits that the native characters in the novel are deindividualized by constantly being referred to as 'Arabs' instead of being appropriated individual names.

The murder of the Arab by a French (Meursault) presents the dehumanizing nature of the French imperialist towards the Arabs who they rule over. Fanon (1961) explains that the state of colonialism perpetuates a great hostility between the colonized and the colonizer. It is this kind of hostility that in a way pushes Meursault to kill the Arab. He reports that:

On seeing me, the Arab raised himself a little, and his hand went to his pocket. Naturally, I gripped Raymond's revolver in the pocket of my coat...I took that step, just one step, forward. And then the Arab drew his and held it up toward me, athwart the sunlight...And so, with that crisp, whipcrack sound, it all began. I shook off my sweat and the clinging veil of light. I knew I'd shattered the balance of the day, the spacious calm of this beach on which I had been happy. But I fired four shots more into the inert body, on which they left no visible trace. And each successive shot was another loud, fateful rap on the door of my undoing. (Camus, 1946, p. 39)

Meursault remains quite indifferent to this murder and is aloof probably, because his victim is of an unimportant race. His vengefulness indicates his hatred towards the Arabs more especially, because he kills the Arab on behalf of his friend, Raymond, who was in direct conflict with the now deceased Arab. Meursault does not lack *mens rea* to murder the Arab as he holds firmly Raymond's pistol which he then uses to shoot dead the Arab. He fires not one, but four bullet shots into the Arab's body. In this case, there is an *actus rea*; the shooting of the Arab which if compounded with Meursault's *mens rea* makes him criminally liable for the death of the Arab.

During Meursault's judicial trial however, he is not prosecuted for murdering an Arab but rather for failing to cry at his mother's funeral. It is as if the French system have connived against the deceased simply because he is an Arab. There is no single Arab who stands at the witness stand in the court so there is never to be an account of what transpired at the beach from the other Arab's perspective. Instead, all witnesses are French, a racist strategy to subvert justice for the Arab. Of interest in this trial is a departed French, Meursault's mother, and it appears that racist inclinations in this novel go beyond life unto death, so that the death of a French is not treated the same as that of an Arab. The Arab death is thus otherized and passes as that of a being who probably deserved to die.

Similarly, the jury investigating Meursault has a parricide case to be heard and, which is elevated to supersede Meursault's trial. Meursault's case is then to be heard with great speed as his lawyer explains, "From what I hear, the court will dispatch your case as quickly as possible, as it isn't the most important one on the Cause List. There is a parricide immediately after, which will take them some time" (Camus, 1946, p. 52). The jury has, therefore, determined that the murder of the Arab is not as grievous as that of a child killing his father and would rather dwell more on the latter. But while the murder of the Arab and the killing of a father involve deaths, Camus is critical that the two cases are not treated equally. The French citizenry is aloof to 'foreign' death ostensibly because Arab lives do no matter.

Disease and Death

This ubiquity of death is also present in Camus' *The Plague*. The setting of the novel is within Oran, a city caught up by the visitation of a deadly pandemic. While Berg (2012) claims that *The Plague* should be

considered as operating on three levels: the story of Oran itself, the Nazi occupation of France, and the human condition itself, Haroutunian (1964) suggests a fourth option, where he views the novel as operating from a metaphorical perspective to denote the patients who suffered from tuberculosis during the time of World War II, as Camus himself did. Haroutunian argues the word “Plague” can be read as “Tuberculosis” and “plague bacillus” as “tubercle bacillus”. Whereas Berg chooses to critic *The Plague* on the second level and Haroutunian reads the novel from the fourth perspective, this paper focuses on the third level, that of human condition, and the existential problem of death. Dr Rieux, Camus’ protagonist in *The Plague* witnesses all the deaths that ensue in Oran and chronicles for us the devastation brought about by the plague.

M. Michel is the first character to be claimed by the plague. It inflicts him with inflamed ganglia and his temperatures rise as high as 104 degrees. Dr Rieux reports the agony of a sick man waiting to die:

His face had gone livid, a grayish green, his lips were bloodless, his breath came in sudden gasps. His limbs spread out by the ganglia, embedded in the berth as if he was trying to bury himself in it or a voice from the depths of the earth was summoning him below, the unhappy man seemed to be stifling under some unseen pressure (Camus, 1948, p. 23)

Camus is vivid in describing the woes of a sick man on the verge of death and underscores illness and death as processes of life. As Sontag explains:

Illness is the night-side of life, a more onerous citizenship. Everyone who is born holds dual citizenship in the kingdom of the well and the kingdom of the sick. Although, we all prefer to use only the good passport, sooner or later each of us is obliged, at least for a spell, to identify ourselves as citizens of that other place (Sontag, 1977, p. 3)

Sontag is emphatic that illness is as inevitable as death and no man can escape it in his lifetime. Camus graphically presents the experience of death and dying to address man’s finitude as a thematic preoccupation in his novel. Sontag views the inevitability of disease and death positively, because for her, awareness of finitude frees the mind and provokes thought in human beings to philosophize on life and death. Dr Rieux for instance has to try to unravel the medical dilemma presented by the plague. Similarly, Camus depicts Michel’s dying experience to show how death resolves all man’s suffering as there is peace in the grave. It is death that ends Michel’s misery and suffering, because in death, he can no longer feel the physical and psychological pain inflicted on him by the plague. In death, therefore, the night-side of life brought by illness comes to a peaceful end and Michel’s body, which is quickly put into isolation can no longer feel the pain.

The second death in the novel is relayed to us through a flashback, Camus’ narrative style that he constantly employs in *The Plague*. We are informed of Camps, a trombone player in the town band, who is depicted as having been a weakling and sickly person, whose chest failed to cope with the heat of the plague. The absurd is manifested in his decision to playing the trombone with a weak chest when it was obvious that such engagement would jeopardize his life. It appears that Camps had been courting death by straining his already weak lungs by continuously blowing the trombone. Tarrou interrogates Camps’ action and reasons that “Camps had joined a band when it was so clearly inadvisable, and what obscure motive had led him to risk his life for the sake of parading the streets on Sunday Mornings” (Camus, 1948, p. 25).

Camps manifests a classic example of what Freud called death drive. Carel (2006) suggests that the theory of death drive heightens Freud’s pessimism by implying that human beings are born evil to the extent that they can harm themselves. Freud (1987) posits that death drive pushes human beings towards selfdestruction and death and this seems the only plausible way of explaining Camps action of repeatedly blowing the trombone. His continuous excitement in trombone blowing, is what Freud terms as death wish,

where one constantly repeats painful scenarios and self-inflicted suffering, all of which amount to expressions of death drive and therefore Camps invites death upon himself. Camps is philosophically aloof to death and chooses to engage in risky routines because even if he were to shun the trombone for the sake of his lungs, he would still die eventually.

The Plague also presents the death of Mr. Othon's son. The child's case is similar to that of M. Michel as the plague has hit the poor soul very intensely. The doctor tries without success to save the child's life. Camus is vivid in describing the agony of a child struggling against all odds to remain alive:

The infection was steadily spreading, and the boy's body putting up no resistance. Tiny, half-formed, but acutely painful buboes were clogging the joints of the child's puny limbs...his eyes shut, his teeth clenched, his features frozen in an agonized grimace, he was rolling his head from side to side on the bolster...From the body, naked under an army of blanket, rose a smell of damp wool and stale sweat. The body had gritted his teeth again...His clawlike fingers were feebly plucking at the sides of the bed. Then they rose, scratched at the blankets over his knees, and suddenly he doubled up his limbs, bringing his thighs above his stomach, and remained quite still. For the first time he opened his eyes...in the small face, rigid as a mask of grayish clay, slowly the lips parted and from them rose a long, incessant scream, hardly varying with his respiration, and filling the ward with a fierce, indignant protest, so little childish that it seemed a collective voice issuing from all the sufferers there (Camus, 1948, p. 192)

All this while, Dr Rieux, Dr Castel, Fr Paneloux, Mr and Mrs Othon, Tarrou and Rambert are in the ward watching helplessly the agony of the child. Rambert on seeing the child's suffering dropped his urge of smoking to watch the distressed body. Dr Rieux is too emotional and failed to hold himself at the sight of the child. The priest had incessantly tried to intercede to God to save the child to no avail. Berg (2012) questions Fr Paneloux's God, who cannot to save the child's life. This demonstrates the powerlessness of religion in solving mundane challenges. Camus cannot reconcile the fact of evil in this universe with belief in God's existence. Onimus captures Camus' thoughts succinctly:

Even if he had not been, for other reasons, full of preconceived ideas with regard to religion, the scandal of evil would probably have been enough to divorce him from it. Caught in the trap, he was never able to untangle this dilemma: either God does not exist and the world is absurd or God exists and it is He, then who is evil (Onimus, 1970, p. 45)

This supposition by Onimus places Camus at loggerheads with God who appears to be self-contradicting because evil exists in the world. Camus is tenacious to disregard this kind of God and views religious antics as inconsequential in the fight against the plague in the city of Oran. His dismissal of religious powers is well articulated in his posthumously published autobiographical novel, *The First Man*. His hero in the novel, Jacques Cormery accounts that in his family "religion had not part in their lives. No one went to Mass, nor one invoked the Ten Commandments, nor did anyone refer to the rewards and punishment of the hereafter" (Camus, 2001, p. 127). Camus rejects religious intervention to the absurd terming such a move as philosophical suicide. Camus rejects Fr Paneloux's attempt to defend God and as Berg (2012) argues, to save the attributes of God in the Oran society is impossible due to the plague and more especially the death of an innocent child.

Dr Castel reports that the child had "put up a surprisingly long resistance" (Camus, 1948, p. 193) and Rieux and Tarrou had in their lives seen children suffer, because since the plague broke out, death had shown no favouritism but never had they watched agony of a child minute by minute. Camus uses the child's death

to depict both the disruptive and democratic nature of death. This early death is also Camus' way to emancipate the soul of the child from a long torturous life; a meaningless life that must end with death.

The novel also presents Fr Paneloux's death. Like Michel and the child, the priest suffers from plagerelated illness and Camus graphically describes his dying experience:

At last, at night fall, Father Paneloux brought up the clot of matter that was choking him; it was red. Even at the height of his fever Paneloux eyes kept their blank serenity, and when, next morning, he was found dead, his body drooping over the bedside, they betrayed nothing (Camus, 1948, p. 209)

Camus' vivid description of the priest's predicament paints a picture of a brutal and agonizing death of a man of God. Fr Paneloux encounters a painful death in isolation. There was no one to assist the poor priest as he battled with death owing to the lonely life he lived. Fr Paneloux's death is not just a mere one but one of a Jesuit militant priest whose belief in God perhaps orchestrated his belief in the afterlife, as put forth by the Gospel of John in the Bible, who quotes Jesus as having said, "I am the resurrection and the life. He who believes in Me, though he may die, he shall live" (John. 11:25). Such a belief of continuity of life beyond the grave offers solace to the Christian believers such as Fr. Paneloux and Meursault's mother in *The Stranger* who die in Christ with anticipation of life in the thereafter.

The medical fraternity also suffers setback as a result of Dr. Richard's death who "too was carried off by the plague..." (Camus, 1948, p. 211). The death occurs at a time when the medics propose to convene a meeting to announce the status of the plague. Camus does not give the particulars of this death, but we know that in this death, he suggests a great deal of irony. While the medical doctors struggle with the plague, it claims one of them and this intensifies the crises in Oran. This death compounds the hopelessness in Oran for even custodians of life are swept by the very plague they are struggling against. But Camus depicts the resilience of the medical doctors for even after the death of their colleague, they don't give up the fight. This is a show of optimistic existentialism, which is Camus' tool used to defeat the absurd. This way of thinking encourages the doctors to confront the plague by tirelessly working in medical laboratories to solve the medical mystery presented by the plague.

The death of Tarrou, Dr Rieux's close friend occurs one evening at a time when the war against the plague is almost successful. In death, Tarrou is remembered as a moralist who constantly sought to help fellow mankind and like Camus, he rejected the idea of death penalty. A Freudian interpretation helps us understand Tarrou's position from his childhood, where he saw his father condemn a man to death and vowed never to follow his father's view on death sentence. Tarrou rejected death penalty all his life arguing that all human beings were condemned, at birth, to inevitable death, hence no one had any moral authority to pronounce death sentence upon any other human being. Though an atheist, Tarrou had struggled to live a virtuous and saint-like life without harming others and constantly posing to question if one could become a saint without God. Tarrou sought to achieve inner peace throughout his life, an accomplishment he attains in his death.

Dr Rieux suffers double tragedy when a day after Tarrou's death, his wife also dies. However, Camus portrays the medical doctor as a character who day by day grows thick skin against death and this explains his "composure on receiving next morning the news of his wife's death" (Camus, 1948, p. 261). He accepts his wife's deaths with equanimity saying that he had expected it and that such suffering was nothing new, because in this time of plague, "for many months, and for the last two days, it was the same selfsame suffering going on and on" (Camus, 1948, p. 261). He consoles his mother not to cry and this portrays him as a strong willed character who is confronting finitude with great strength because the plague had "forced on him a detachment which, try as he might, he couldn't think away..." (Camus, 1948, p. 263).

CONCLUSION

This paper has examined death as a major preoccupation in *The Stranger* and *The Plague*. The various deaths of characters in the two texts have been analyzed to show how each death interrelates with the notion of confronting human finitude with philosophic aloofness, as a result demystifying and deconstructing death as an inevitable phenomenon.

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